

Supplementary Material for the submission titled Children’s and Adolescents’
 Anthropomorphic Conceptions of Social Robots and Chatbots – A Systematic Literature
 Review

Search queries for social robot-related articles

Datebase	Query and Filter
ACM Digital Library	Query: (Fulltext:("student*" or "child*") AND Fulltext:("social robot*" OR (robot* AND (humanoid OR human-like))) AND Fulltext:("misconception*" or "conception*" or "think*" or "understand*" or "learn*")) Filter: Article Type: Research Article, E-Publication Date: Past 5 years, ACM Content: DL
IEEE Xplore	Query: (("Abstract": "student*" OR "child*") AND ("Full Text AND Metadata": "social robot*" OR ("robot*" AND ("humanoid" OR "human-like")))) AND ("Full Text AND Metadata": "misconception*" OR "conception*" OR "think*" OR "understand*" OR "learn*")) Filter: Conferences, Journals, 2019-2024
Scopus	Query: (ABS((student* OR child*) AND ("social robot*" OR (robot* AND (humanoid OR human-like))) AND (misconception* OR conception* OR understand* OR learn OR think*)) AND PUBYEAR > 2018) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE , "j") OR LIMIT-TO(SRCTYPE,"p")) AND (LIMIT-TO(DOCTYPE,"cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE,"English"))

Search queries for chatbot-related articles

Datebase	Query and Filter
ACM Digital Library	Query: (Fulltext:("student*" or "child*") AND Fulltext:("chatbot*" or "assistant*") AND Fulltext:("misconception*" or "conception*" or "think*" or "understand*" or "learn*")) Filter: Article Type: Research Article, E-Publication Date: Past 5 years, ACM Content: DL
IEEE Xplore	Query: (("Abstract": "student*" OR "child*") AND ("Full Text AND Metadata": "chatbot*" OR "assistant*") AND ("Full Text AND Metadata": "misconception*" OR "conception*" OR "think*" OR "understand*" OR "learn*")) Filter: Conferences, Journals, 2019-2024
Scopus	Query: (ABS((student* OR child*) AND (chatbot* OR assistant*) AND (misconception* OR conception* OR understand* OR learn OR think*)) AND PUBYEAR > 2018) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE , "j") OR LIMIT-TO(SRCTYPE,"p")) AND (LIMIT-TO(DOCTYPE,"cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE,"English"))